

On Generalised Pair Potential-Binding Energy, Dissociation Energy and Electron Affinity of Alkali Halide Molecules

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The generalised pair potential of Woodcock has been used to compare various properties of nineteen gaseous alkali halide molecules. These properties include binding energy, dissociation energy and electron affinity. The agreement between theoretical and experimental value is quite satisfactory showing the validity of the generalised pair potential.

THEORETICAL evaluation of molecular properties of alkali halide gaseous molecules using interaction potential has attracted the attention of a number of workers¹⁻¹⁴ during recent years. The aim of such calculation is to test the validity of the specific form of interaction potential by comparing the theoretically computed properties with experimental ones. Secondly the relative merits of the various empirical interionic potential functions can be assessed. In most cases two term potentials corresponding to a simple ionic model have been used. These two term potentials were found to be inadequate for experimental data on gaseous alkali halide ion pairs. In the year 1974, Woodcock¹⁵ proposed a generalised three term potential and used this to compute various properties of gaseous alkali metal halides. Here in case of alkali halide molecules we have used the generalised pair potential of Woodcock which can be written as :

$$U_{(R)} = AR^{-m} \exp[-B(R^n - 1)] - e^2 R^{-1} \quad \dots (1)$$

where e is the electronic charge, R is the internuclear separation, A and B are the potential parameters and the values of m and n are different for different crystals. In the present paper we have evaluated binding energy, dissociation energy and electron affinity of alkali halide molecules using this generalised pair potential.

Theory :

Applying the familiar molecular stability and force constant condition^{5,17}

$$\begin{aligned} U'_{(R)} &= 0 &&) \\ &&&) \text{ at } R = r_e \quad \dots (2) \\ U''_{(R)} &= k_e &&) \end{aligned}$$

to equation (1) one obtains

$$A = \frac{e^2}{r_e^{1-m} \exp[-B(r_e^n - 1)] (m+n Br_e^n)} \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\text{and } B = [-x + (X^2 - 4YZ)]^{\frac{1}{2}} (2Y)^{-1} \quad \dots (4)$$

$$\text{where } x = r_e^n \left\{ 2mn - n^3 - \frac{nr_e}{e^2} (k_e r_e^2 + \frac{e^2}{r_e}) \right\}$$

$$Y = n^2 r_e^{2n}$$

$$Z = m^2 - \frac{mr_e^2}{e^2} k_e r_e^2 + \frac{e^2}{r_e}$$

The binding energy D_i is given by

$$D_i = -U(r_e) \quad \dots (5)$$

$$\text{So that } D_i = \frac{e^2}{r_e} \left[1 - \frac{1}{(m+n Br_e^n)} \right] \quad \dots (6)$$

The dissociation energy D_e , can be obtained from the equation

$$D_e = E - I + D_i \quad \dots (7)$$

Inserting the value of D_i from (6) one gets

$$D_e = E - I + \frac{e^2}{r_e} \left(1 - \frac{1}{m+n Br_e^n} \right) \quad \dots (8)$$

where I is the ionisation potential of alkali atom, and E is the electron affinity of the halogen atom.

Results and Discussion

In order to calculate the various properties of alkali halide molecules the experimental values of r_e and k_e were taken from different sources^{7,12,16,17}. The values of m and n are taken from the work of Woodcock. The calculated values of binding energy from equation (6) are listed in the second column of table. The experimental value of D_i are also given in the third and fourth column for comparison. The agreement seems to be good considering the limitations in the theoretical approach and uncertainties involved in the experimental binding

TABLE I—THEORETICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL VALUES OF BINDING ENERGY, DISSOCIATION ENERGY AND ELECTRON AFFINITY OF ALKALI HALIDE MOLECULES IN K. J./MOLE.

Molecules	D_i (Calc.)	D_i (exp)	D_i (obs)	D_e	D_e	E	E	E
		Ref(8)	Ref(7)	(calc)	(exp)	(cal)	(mean)	(exp)
LiF	727.1	745.8	770.3	534.1	574.1	367.0		
NaF	626.9	603.98	643.9	458.2	448.6	317.5		
KF	557.3	586.6	582.4	465.7	482.4	343.8	357.92	327* ⁺
RbF	536.6	548.99	558.98	460.8	516.2	382.5		324.4 ⁺
CsF	527.3	524.87	546.0	478.9	530.6	378.8		
LiCl	585.1	656.1	641.4	418.2	482.4	417.3		
NaCl	507.9	536.5	554.8	365.2	409.1	397.0		
KCl	456.7	480.5	493.7	391.1	424.4	386.4	396.66	353* ⁺
RbCl	442.7	466.98	474.5	392.9	434.2	394.4		348 ⁺
CsCl	431.1	445.8	469.9	408.7	443.8	388.2		
LiBr	545.9	619.4	618.4	321.1	419.7	393.8		
NaBr	481.1	515.2	534.3	280.5	366.6	381.3		
KBr	537.1	459.3	475.3	313.6	380.1	361.7	375.36	295.2* ⁺
RbBr	417.0	444.8	456.1	309.3	385.9	371.8		324.3 ⁺
CsBr	402.9	427.4	454.4	322.6	395.6	368.2		
LiI	499.3	580.8	580.3	289.0	337.7	358.4		
NaI	447.2	485.3	503.3	261.1	296.2	344.8		309.7* ⁺
RbI	388.7	414.9	426.3	295.5	323.2	337.4	342.2	295.4 ⁺
CsI	375.4	412.9	423.0	309.6	328.0	328.1		

Average % error -5.2%, -7.9%, -13.8%

*Schmidt Bocking & Bethge (1973)

+Berry & Reimen (1963)

energies. In the case of binding energy the mean percentage deviation between calculated and experimental values is not more than 7.9 percent. The calculated values of dissociation energy D_e according to Woodcock potential (1) using equation (8) are given in fifth column. The experimental values of dissociation energy are also listed in sixth column. The percentage deviation between theoretical and experimental values of dissociation energy is 13.8 percent. It is interesting to note that the calculated values of D_i and D_e are less than the observed values. The results of calculation can be improved if we consider the Van der Waals and dipole-quadrupole terms in the Woodcock potential. Such terms will give additional contribution to the interaction energy. The overall agreement is satisfactory. The electron affinity of halogen atoms were obtained from equation (8) and are recorded in the seventh column of the table. For the calculation of electron affinity, the experimental D_e values have been used. The average values of the electron affinity for halogens are compared with the experimental values of Schmidt-Bocking Bethge²¹ and Berry-Reimann²². While calculating the values of D_i and D_e , the experimental values of E and I were taken respectively from the work of Bocking *et al*²¹ and Massey²⁰. The agreement between theoretical and experimental values of electron affinity is also satisfactory.

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References

1. M. BORN and J. E. MAYER, *Z. Phys.*, 1932, **75**, 1.
2. H. HELLMANN, *Actaphysicochem.*, U.S.S.R., 1934, **1**, 913.
3. J. A. WASASTJERNA, *Phil. Trans.*, 1938, **A237**, 105.
4. Y. P. VARSHNI and R. C. SHUKLA, *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, 1963, **35**, 130
5. M. P. TOSI, *Solid State Phys.*, 1964, **16**, 1.
6. R. L. REDINGTON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, **74**, 181.
7. P. S. BRUMER and M. KARPLUS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1973, **58**, 3903.
8. Y. P. VARSHNI and R. C. SHUKLA, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, **35**, 582.
9. J. D. PANDEY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 251.
10. C. M. KACHHAVA and S. C. SAXENA, *Indian J. Pure and Appl. Phys.*, 1965, **3**, 178.
11. C. M. KACHHAVA and S. C. SAXENA, *Mol. Phys.*, 1964, **7**, 465.
12. J. D. PANDEY, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 1315; *J. Phys. B. Atom molec. Phys.*, 1970, **3**, 925.
13. V. B. GOHEL and M. P. TRIVEDI, *Indian J. Pure and Appl. Phys.*, 1972, **10**, 474
14. S. NOOR MOHAMMAD, *Indian J. Pure and Appl. Phys.*, 1978, **16**, 646.
15. L. V. WOODCOCK, *J. Chem. Soc. Faraday Trans II*, 1974, **70**, 1405.
16. D. DUBICHOIOTTI, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, **34**, 2189.
17. Y. P. VARSHNI and R. C. SHUKLA, *J. Mol. Spectro*, 1965, **16**, 63.
18. E. S. RITNER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1951, **19**, 1030.
19. A. G. GAYDON, *Dissociation energies*, (Chapman and Hall, London, 1953).
20. A. G. MASSEY, *The typical elements* (Penguin, England, 1972).
21. H. B. SCHMIDT and K. J. BETHGE, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1973, **58**, 3244.
22. R. S. BERRY and C. W. REIMANN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1963, **38**, 1540.